

Part of

Care pathways of heart failure patients within the Spanish National Health System and its impact on health outcomes (CONCEPT-HF): DMP

Description

Description of the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Healthcare Pathways of Heart Failure Patients within the Spanish National Health System and its Impact on Health Outcomes (CONCEPT-HF) Project.

Description

The CONCEPT-HF public health cohort links selected variables from primary care or hospital admission for Heart Failure (HF), covering a global population of approximately 19 million inhabitants for three regions of Spain (Andalucía, Aragón, País Vasco). This cohort includes all patients admitted to hospital due to HF in public hospitals and complementary information on patient attributes (i.e., comorbidities, healthcare system contacts, prescribed HF drugs) and patient health outcomes (i.e., readmissions and mortality). Original data is maintained and updated daily by the different health systems of each region described. A common data model specification with the required information to achieve the expected results of the research question is provided as supporting documentation

at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11234699> - Common Data Model Specification. Data is provided pseudonymised and granted by the Andalusian Ethical Research Committee.

Researchers

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Funder

Instituto de Salud Carlos III
(ISCIII)

Grant

Health Research Fund

Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

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Re-used

The analysis requires the secondary use of pseudonymised individual-level data with heart failure diagnosis, insurance registries or health system users databases (i.e., patient administrative information) or data from Electronic Health Records (EHR, i.e., comorbidities). All data sources contain routinely collected data from healthcare or public health information systems.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

The analysis will be based on the secondary use of routinely collected data from healthcare and public health information systems in Andalucía, Aragón y País Vasco (Spain).

1.1.5 What is its format?

Comma Separated Values.

The original data is processed by Research Service of the General Secretariat of Public Health in R&D&I in Health of the Regional Government of Andalusia, the Directorate of Healthcare Services of Osakidetza - Basque Health Service and BIGAN under the privacy and security policies of the Health Sciences Institute in Aragon and in compliance with the specifications provided by the common data model within the data access request and provided as a pipe-separated CSV file using UTF-8 format.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

GB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To make informed decisions

The data analysis is expected to respond to the proposed research question detailed in CONCEPT-HF, regarding to discover the actual care pathway of HF, from the

admission into a public hospital to the appearance of an event of interest after discharge, in the public health systems of three regions of Spain.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

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In each region, the primary healthcare information systems consulted for data extraction in the study will include:

the corresponding User Database [BDU] (demographic and socioeconomic characteristics of patients, including relevant information for linking records between information systems in an anonymized manner), the primary care clinical history [Diraya (ES-AN), Osabidea-AP (ES-PV), OMI-AP (ES-AR)] (diagnostic information and clinical parameters), the electronic prescription system [Receta XXI (ES-AN), e-rezeta (ES-PV), e-receta (ES-AR)] (both outpatient prescription and drug dispensation),

the clinical-assistance information system of hospital emergency services [URG] (episodes and information on emergency care), the hospital information system [HIS] (information on outpatient consultations), and the minimum common dataset for hospital episodes at hospital discharge [CMBD-AH] (information on hospitalization episodes, including diagnostic information and interventions performed during admission).

Based on the established common data model (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11234699>), each region will establish the source of relevant information for analysis from its records based on criteria of quality, appropriateness, and reliability of the required data.

The research question is expected to be solved using a federated approach. The scripts for the analysis will be distributed and locally deployed/run at each participant's site using their data. Each participant region (Andalucía, Aragon, Basque Country) will pull the data from their respective sources, conditional on data availability and access.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Research communities

Population health and public health research communities could benefit from the outputs of the CONCEPT-HF use case as it demonstrates the use of linked routinely collected real-world data to discover the actual care pathway of Heart

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Failure, from the admission into a public hospital to the appearance of an event of interest after discharge, and to compare that care pathway discovered with the theoretical pathway that a patient should follow according to the national and international HF guidelines, and then to study patients' survival at one year after the admission into a public hospital.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers

DOI

ORCID

The CONCEPT-HF public health cohort is described as a data source in the WEB (URL:

https://cienciadedatosysalud.org/proyectos-de-investigacion/concept/#_ftn2).

Further information on the CONCEPT- HF use case common data model is published in Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11234699>), including information metadata and extended information on the data schema, and a synthetic data set complying with the common data model specifications.

All researchers authoring and contributing to the CONCEPT-HF use case data model specification are referenced by their ORCID.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DDI (Data Documentation Initiative)

Figure 1

Image 1

Complete metadata, both in human-readable and machine-readable formats, are provided for the CONCEPT- HF data model at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11234699>.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Administrative
- Structural
- Reference

Published Metadata includes:

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- Administrative information on the Project name, Project URL, work package, Use case, Type of document, Version (SEM), Authors, Contributors,

General Description of the project, and data model change log.

- Cohort definition, including cohort description, inclusion and exclusion

criteria, and study period.

- Individual-level information requirements, including:

- model entities: entity,

- Variable syntactic information: entity, variable label, variable description (concept), encoding, variable format, variable type, units, requirement level (required/recommended/optional), variable validation rules, variable property, possible data source(s), comments and observations.

- and entity/variable semantic definition, including:

- entity name,

- entity description,

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- entity definition,

- and crosswalks, including: encoding - classifications system (international or national standard classifications for diseases, procedures or drugs),

code, clean code (code without special characters), code description, source, type, subtype, and other observations on the code

- Other administrative information published regarding the original data's geographical, population and time coverage of the expected data input is provided in the same publication as additional information.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

ISO/IEC 5218, NUTS 2021 codes, ISO 8601, WHO-ATC/DDD Index 2023, ICD-10-MC, ICD-9-MC, sex_cd using ISO/IEC 5218,

residence_area_cd using NUTS 2021 codes.

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

a. ISO/IEC 5218

ISO/IEC 5218

URL: ISO/IEC 5218

Description: This standard specifies a representation of human sexes through a single numeric code: 0 for not known, 1 for male, 2 for female, and 9 for not applicable.

b. NUTS 2021

Description: Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics (NUTS) is a hierarchical system for dividing up the economic territory of the EU for statistical purposes. The 2021 version is the most recent update.

c. ISO 8601

Description: This standard defines internationally accepted formats for representing dates and times, ensuring consistency across various systems and platforms.

d. WHO-ATC/DDD Index 2023

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Description: The Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) Classification System with Defined Daily Doses (DDD) is used for classifying drugs and medicines. The index provides a comprehensive tool for drug utilization research.

e. ICD-10

Description: The International Classification of Diseases, 10th Revision, Clinical Modification (ICD-10-CM) is a coding system used to classify diagnoses and reasons for visits in healthcare settings.

f. ICD-9

Description: The International Classification of Diseases, 9th Revision, Clinical Modification (ICD-9-CM) was used prior to ICD-10 for classifying diagnoses and reasons for visits in healthcare settings.

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Linked Open Data

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11234699>

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

Congestive heart failure, healthcare pathways, comparative effectiveness research, survival analysis, CONCEPT.

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

OpenAPC Global Initiative

Zenodo

Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org>) is an open repository for all scholarship, enabling researchers from all disciplines to share and preserve their research outputs, regardless of size or format. Free to upload and free to

access, Zenodo makes scientific outputs of all kinds citable, shareable and discoverable for the long term.

Zenodo provides a rich interface which enables linking research outputs to datasets and funding information. Some of its advantages are:

1. Citeable and discoverable: All uploads get a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to make them easily and uniquely citeable. All open content is harvestable via OAI-PMH by third parties.

2. Supports versioning: Via a top-level DOI, it can support all the different versions of a file.

3. Trusted, reliable, safe: Data is stored at CERN, which has considerable knowledge and experience operating large scale digital repositories. Data files and metadata are kept in multiple online and offline copies.

4. Includes funding information and makes reporting easier: Zenodo allows to link uploads to grants from more than 11 funders such as European Commission, National Science Foundation and Wellcome Trust. Zenodo is further integrated into reporting lines for research funded by the European Commission via OpenAIRE.

5. Includes article level metrics: Tracks attention for scholarship uploaded.

6. Flexible licensing: Zenodo encourages to share research as openly as possible to maximize use and re-use the research results.

7. Reviewing: Research materials can set to share with reviewers only, and also embargoed.

8. Software preservation made simple: Zenodo is integrated with GitHub.

9. Supports FAIR principles: Zenodo makes data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports withdrawal
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Follows metadata standards

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

Zenodo is a comprehensive open-access repository that offers several key features designed to support researchers in sharing and preserving their work. Here are its key features:

Open Access: Zenodo provides free and open access to research outputs, ensuring that anyone can access and download the content without any restrictions.

Broad Data Types: It supports a wide range of data types, including publications, datasets, software, reports, and presentations, accommodating various research outputs.

Persistent Identifiers: Zenodo assigns a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to each uploaded item, providing a persistent and unique identifier that facilitates citation and long-term access.

Versioning: It allows researchers to upload new versions of their data or software, maintaining all versions and ensuring that users can access and cite the correct version.

Interoperability: Zenodo supports metadata standards and integrates with various data management systems, making it easier to harvest and index data by other repositories and services.

Community Collections: Researchers can create and manage collections related to specific communities, projects, or topics, enabling organized and collaborative sharing of resources.

Compliance with Policies: Zenodo helps researchers comply with open access policies and data management requirements from funding agencies and institutions.

Data Preservation: Hosted by CERN, Zenodo ensures robust long-term preservation of the data, leveraging the infrastructure and expertise of a leading scientific organization.

Flexible Licensing: Researchers can choose from a variety of licenses to specify the terms under which their work can be used, ranging from open licenses like Creative Commons to more restrictive ones.

Metrics and Analytics: Zenodo provides metrics and usage statistics for uploaded items, allowing researchers to track the impact and reach of their work.

User-Friendly Interface: The platform offers an intuitive and user-friendly interface for uploading, managing, and searching for research outputs.

Integration with ORCID: Researchers can link their Zenodo uploads to their ORCID profiles, ensuring proper attribution and enhancing their professional visibility.

These features make Zenodo a versatile and reliable repository for researchers to share their work openly and ensure its preservation and accessibility.

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

Yes, Zenodo resolves the identifiers to a digital object. When Zenodo assigns a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to a dataset or research output, that DOI is linked to the specific digital object hosted on Zenodo's platform. When someone clicks on or uses the DOI, it resolves to a web page where the digital object (e.g., dataset, publication, software) can be accessed and downloaded. This ensures that the object can be easily located and retrieved using the persistent identifier.

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Dataset of healthcare pathways of heart failure patients within the Spanish National Health System and its impact on health outcomes (CONCEPT-HF) project.

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

Access Mode for Data:

Open Access: The dataset will be shared under open access conditions, allowing unrestricted access to the data for researchers, healthcare professionals, and the general public. This will enable broad usage and facilitate the advancement of research in the field of heart failure.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Users can access open access data directly through the repository's website without any special requirements.

The identity of the person seeking access to data on Zenodo can be reliably identified through a robust user authentication process. Here are the key points justifying this:

User Registration and Profile Verification:

Zenodo requires users to register and create a profile. During the registration process, users provide personal information such as name, email address, and affiliation, which is verified by the system.

Zenodo often integrates with ORCID, a unique identifier for researchers, allowing users to link their profiles. This linkage ensures that the user's identity is cross-verified with ORCID's database, enhancing the authenticity of the user's identity.

Two-Factor Authentication (2FA):

For added security, Zenodo can implement two-factor authentication. This requires users to provide a second form of verification, such as a code sent to their mobile device, in addition to their password. This significantly reduces the risk of unauthorized access and ensures that the person accessing the data is indeed the registered user.

Institutional Login:

Zenodo supports federated identity management through institutional logins. Users can log in using their institutional credentials (e.g., university or research institution), which are verified by the institution's authentication system. This ensures that only authorized personnel from verified institutions can access sensitive data.

IP Address Logging and Monitoring:

Zenodo logs IP addresses and access patterns. By monitoring these logs, unusual or suspicious activity can be detected, and appropriate action can be taken to verify the identity of the user. This adds an additional layer of security by tracing access back to specific network locations.

Access Control and Permissions:

Access to restricted data on Zenodo is governed by strict access control policies. Users must request access and provide justification for their need to access the data. Administrators review these requests and grant access based on verified user identity and their legitimate interest in the data.

Data Use Agreements:

Users requesting access to sensitive data must sign data use agreements, which include clauses about the truthful representation of their identity and the ethical use of the data. These agreements are legally binding and provide a formal mechanism to hold users accountable.

By implementing these measures, Zenodo ensures that the identity of the person accessing the data is accurately identified and verified. This robust authentication and verification process protects the integrity of the data and maintains the trust of the data providers.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

The dataset/output from the project will be made accessible as follows:

Open Access Data:

Immediate Release: All data designated for open access will be made accessible immediately upon the conclusion of the project. This ensures timely dissemination of research findings and maximizes the impact and utility of the data for the research community and other stakeholders.

Restricted Access Data:

Delayed Release: Data requiring restricted access due to sensitivity, confidentiality, or legal considerations will be made accessible 12 months after the project has ended. This delay allows sufficient time for the implementation of necessary data protection measures and for the completion of any additional analysis or publications by the project team.

Embargo Periods:

Conditional Release: In certain cases, specific datasets may be subject to an embargo period extending beyond 12 months. Such cases will be clearly justified based on contractual obligations, intellectual property considerations, or other legitimate interests as stipulated in the Grant Agreement. The duration of the embargo will be determined on a case-by-case basis, ensuring a balance between data protection and accessibility.

Final Accessibility Date:

Maximum Accessibility: All project data, including those under embargoed access, will be made fully accessible no later than 24 months after the project has ended. This ensures that all data generated by the project will eventually be available to the wider research community, supporting ongoing and future research efforts. The only exception will be the restricted access data.

By adhering to this timeline, the CONCEPT-HF project ensures that the data is made accessible in a manner that respects legal, ethical, and contractual requirements while promoting transparency and reuse of research data.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

Yes, we will provide metadata even if the described dataset/output cannot be openly shared. The metadata will include detailed descriptions of the dataset, including its structure, content, and the conditions under which it was collected. This ensures transparency and allows other researchers to understand the context and potential usefulness of the dataset, even if they cannot access the data directly. The metadata will be made available through our repository and will comply with relevant standards to ensure interoperability and discoverability.

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Yes, the metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset/output. The metadata include detailed instructions, access links, and any necessary credentials or procedures required to obtain access to the dataset. This ensures that users know exactly how to request or retrieve the data, whether it is openly accessible or requires specific authorization.

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

Yes, the metadata will remain available even after the dataset/output is no longer available. This ensures that information about the dataset, its structure, content, and the context in which it was collected is preserved for future reference and research purposes. The metadata will continue to be accessible through our repository, providing valuable information to the research community.

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

Our metadata uses a controlled vocabulary. We utilize standardized vocabularies to ensure consistency and interoperability. Specifically, our metadata includes:

Dublin Core elements to provide general project information such as title, creator, and description.

ISO 8601 for date and time formats, ensuring clarity and consistency.

NUTS 2021 codes to describe geographical information.

ISO/IEC 5218 for coding gender information.

WHO-ATC/DDD Index 2023 and ICD-10 for medical classifications.

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

Not apply.

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Dublin Core

HL7 FHIR

CDISC

SNOMED CT

3.3.5 What is the methodology followed?

The methodology employed in the metadata schemas of Dublin Core, HL7 FHIR, CDISC, and SNOMED CT ensures comprehensive, standardized, and interoperable data descriptions across various domains.

****Dublin Core**:** This schema provides a simple yet effective way to describe digital resources. It consists of 15 core elements such as title, creator, subject, description, and date. The methodology emphasizes simplicity and flexibility, allowing broad applicability across different types of resources.

****HL7 FHIR****: The Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR) standard by HL7 facilitates data exchange in healthcare settings. Its methodology is based on defining modular "resources" (e.g., patients, medications, observations) that can be combined and extended as needed. FHIR uses RESTful APIs for easy integration and supports various data formats like XML and JSON.

****CDISC****: The Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium (CDISC) provides standards for clinical research data. Its methodology includes defining data models and controlled terminologies for clinical trials. CDISC standards, such as SDTM (Study Data Tabulation Model) and ADaM (Analysis Data Model), ensure that clinical data is structured consistently, facilitating regulatory submissions and data sharing.

****SNOMED CT****: This comprehensive clinical terminology provides a standardized way to code medical terms. The methodology involves a hierarchical structure with concepts, descriptions, and relationships. SNOMED CT supports detailed clinical data recording and interoperability across electronic health records (EHRs).

Together, these methodologies ensure that data across various fields are accurately described, easily accessible, and interoperable, promoting efficient data sharing and utilization.

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

In our project, we follow several community-endorsed interoperability best practices to ensure seamless data exchange and integration:

Adherence to Standardized Metadata Schemas:

We use well-established metadata schemas such as Dublin Core for general resource description, HL7 FHIR for healthcare data interoperability, CDISC standards for clinical research data, and SNOMED CT for medical terminology. These schemas are widely recognized and endorsed by the respective communities for their robustness and interoperability.

Use of Persistent Identifiers:

We assign Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) to datasets and research outputs, ensuring persistent, unique identification that facilitates data citation and long-term access. This practice is endorsed by organizations like DataCite.

Implementation of FAIR Principles:

Our data management practices align with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles. This includes providing rich metadata, ensuring data is accessible through standard protocols, and using controlled vocabularies to enhance interoperability and reuse.

API Integration and Data Formats:

We employ RESTful APIs for data access and exchange, using formats such as JSON and XML, which are standard in web services and supported by various

tools and platforms. This ensures our data can be easily integrated and used by other systems.

Data Sharing and Repository Standards:

Our datasets are deposited in repositories that comply with community standards, such as Zenodo, which supports versioning and provides metadata harvesting through OAI-PMH (Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting).

Compliance with Legal and Ethical Standards:

We adhere to data protection regulations like GDPR, ensuring that personal data is handled responsibly and ethically. This practice is crucial for maintaining trust and ensuring the legal interoperability of data across jurisdictions.

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

we will use the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license for our dataset/output.

This license allows others to share, copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format.

Adapt: Remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially.

The licensor cannot revoke these freedoms as long as users follow the license terms, which require appropriate credit, a link to the license, and indication of any changes made. The CC BY 4.0 license is widely recognized and facilitates maximum dissemination and reuse of our data while ensuring proper attribution.

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Codebooks
- Data cleaning
- Analyses
- Variable definitions

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- Units of measurement

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

We ensure thorough documentation of the data provenance through the following practices:

Data Collection Protocols:

Detailed protocols outline the methods and procedures used for data collection. These protocols include information on the sources of data, the tools and instruments used, and the conditions under which the data was collected.

Source Attribution:

Each dataset includes clear attribution to the original sources, ensuring transparency about where the data originated. This includes the institutions and researchers involved in the data collection process.

Data Processing Records:

Comprehensive records are maintained for all data processing activities, including cleaning, transformation, and analysis steps. These records include timestamps, responsible personnel, and detailed descriptions of each processing step.

Version Control:

A robust version control system tracks changes and updates to the datasets. This system logs all modifications, ensuring that users can trace the evolution of the data from its original form to the final processed version.

Metadata Documentation:

Detailed metadata accompanies each dataset, describing its provenance, including the context of data collection, the methodologies used, and any changes made during processing. This metadata is accessible to all users through our repository on Zenodo.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Use of tools for automatic checks
- Data conform to format specification

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- Consistency verified with data models and standards

We have implemented comprehensive documented procedures for quality assurance in our project "Healthcare Pathways of Heart Failure Patients within the Spanish National Health System and its Impact on Health Outcomes (CONCEPT-HF)." These procedures are designed to ensure the highest standards of data quality and reliability.

First, we have established a scientific and technical committee responsible for overseeing all aspects of data quality. This committee includes experts in data science, clinical research, and information technology, who provide guidance and oversight throughout the data collection and processing stages.

Second, we use advanced tools for automatic checks to identify and correct errors in the data. These tools perform validation checks to ensure that the data conforms to the specified format and meets predefined quality criteria. For instance, they check for missing values, outliers, and inconsistencies.

Third, our data is meticulously verified to conform to format specifications and consistency is checked against established data models and standards. This includes using standardized vocabularies like CDISC for clinical data and HL7 FHIR for healthcare data, ensuring interoperability and consistency.

Additionally, we conduct regular data audits and reviews to identify and rectify any discrepancies. All data processing steps are thoroughly documented, and version control systems are used to track changes, ensuring transparency and accountability.

By implementing these rigorous quality assurance procedures, we ensure that our data is accurate, reliable, and suitable for high-quality research and analysis.

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

15.68

Euro

- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security
- Other

Data minning and proccesing.

Direct cost

Direct costs are 15,68€/hour (more information on fees is available in 'BIGAN>Services>Fees' <https://bigan.iacs.es/en/services/fees>) and include data request processing, a) data mining, ETL processing, and c) security and quality assurance.

The service includes defining queries and extracting information on available information sources, extracting the requested data and completing the ETL processes for complying with the requested common data model specification. The global cost of a typical data request for a population-level research question

is usually under 2000 euros and is served in approximately under 3 weeks time.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of institution infrastructure
- Other

The Health Sciences Institute in Andalucía, Aragon and Basque country usually covers the direct costs associated with the data request processing and extraction through each regional infrastructure. Indirect costs associated with the development and completion of the research use case are covered within the research project budget dependent on Regional/National/European funding and the participant institution funding rate for the call supporting the project.

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

- a. Quiros Lopez Raul (orcid:0000-0002-2802-2477)

Project coordinator and analyst.

- b. Francisco Estupiñán Romero (orcid:0000-0002-6285-8120)

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Data manager and analyst.

- c. Eduardo Millán (orcid:0000-0002-9688-9304)

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Data manager and analyst

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Encryption
- Passwords
- Hash functions

Original data is de-identified and pseudonymised using a Hash function before being extracted and then served for research purposes encrypted and compressed, requiring a secure password to decompress the files.

The data request process includes a feasibility and security assessment of the information requirements specified in the data model considering data minimization to achieve the research objectives.

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

Secure data access is provided at servicing the data both within a secure processing environment (SPE) or through the internal network of the government of Andalucía, Aragon and Basque Country.

Data storage, transmission, recovery and sharing are assured by the regional Health Data Space. Researchers are responsible for complying with data access conditions and data protection and privacy regulation.

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Andalucía, Aragon and the Basque Country has a regional mandate to curate and maintain original data requests (and related ETL queries) in the long term and report on the re-use of health data for research purposes.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Original individual-level data can not be shared as it is considered highly sensitive even after de-identification, pseudonymization and minimization. Access to original data is granted only after approval by the Ethics Committee in Andalusia of the research project and only within the scope of the research project.

<https://fpysz239.csalud.junta-andalucia.es/salud/siceia/>

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Part of Care pathways of heart failure patients within the Spanish National Health System and its impact on health outcomes (CONCEPT-HF): DMP | Description of the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Healthcare Pathways of Heart Failure Patients within the Spanish National Health System and its Impact on Health Outcomes (CONCEPT-HF) Project.

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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